

UMUMLASHGAN HILFER MA'NOSIDAGI HOSILA VA RIMAN-LIUUVILL
MA'NOSIDAGI INTEGRALNI O'Z ICHIGA OLUVCHI ODDIY DIFFERENSIAL
TENGLAMA UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI

ЗАДАЧА КОШИ ДЛЯ ОБЫКНОВЕННОГО ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЛЬНОГО
УРАВНЕНИЯ С ПРОИЗВОДНОЙ В ОБОБЩЕННОМ СМЫСЛЕ ГИЛЬФЕРА И
ИНТЕГРАЛОМ В СМЫСЛЕ РИМАНА-ЛИУВИЛЯ

THE CAUCHY PROBLEM FOR AN ORDINARY DIFFERENTIAL EQUATION
INVOLVING THE DERIVATIVE IN THE GENERALIZED HILFER SENSE AND THE
INTEGRAL IN THE RIEMAN-LIOUVILLE SENSE

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Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada umumlashgan hilfer ma'nosidagi hosila va riman-liuuvill ma'nosidagi integralni o'z ichiga oluvchi oddiy differensial tenglama uchun koshi masalasi o'rganilgan. Masalaning yechimi Mittag-Leffler funksiyasi yordamida topilgan. Berilgan funksiya yetarli shart topilgan va teorema shaklida bayon qilingan hamda bu teorema isbotlangan.*

Аннотация: *В статье исследуется задача Коши для обыкновенного дифференциального уравнения, содержащего производную в обобщенном смысле Гильфера и интеграл в смысле Римана-Лиувилля. Решение задачи было найдено с помощью функции Mittag-Леффлера, для данной функции найдено достаточное условие, которое сформулировано в виде теоремы, и эта теорема доказана.*

Abstract: *In this article, the Cauchy problem for an ordinary differential equation containing a derivative in the generalized Hilfer sense and an integral in the Riemann-Liouville sense is studied. The solution to the problem was found using the Mittag-Leffler function. A sufficient condition was found for the given function and it was stated in the form of a theorem, and this theorem was proved.*

Kalit so'zlar: *oddiy differensial tenglama, kasr tartibli operator, Koshi masalasi.*

Ключевые слова: *обыкновенное дифференциальное уравнение, оператор дробного порядка, задача Коши.*

Keywords: *ordinary differential equation, fractional order operator, Cauchy problem.*

I.Kirish. *So'ngi vaqtlarda kasr tartibli integro-differensial operatorlar qatnashgan differensial tenglamalar bilan shug'ullanishga bo'lgan qiziqish ortib bormoqda. Bunga sabab ko'plab issiqlik tarqalish va diffuziya jarayonlarini matematik modelini tuzish*

funksiyani biror qiymati qatnashgan differensial tenglama uchun qo'yiladigan masalalarga keltiriladi. Kasr tartibli integro-differensial operatorlar qatnashgan xususiy hosilali va oddiy differensial tenglamalar ko'plab tadqiqotchilar tomonidan o'rganilgan. Masalan [1-3] ishlarga qaralsin.

II. Masalaning qo'yilishi.

(0,1) oraliqda ushbu

$$D_{0x}^{(\alpha,\varphi),\beta} y(x) - \lambda I_{0x}^\gamma y(x) = f(x) \tag{1}$$

kasr tartibli oddiy differensial tenglamani qaraylik, bu yerda $y(x)$ -noma'lum funksiya, $f(x)$ – berilgan funksiya; $\alpha, \varphi, \beta, \lambda$ -o'zgarmas haqiqiy sonlar bo'lib, $0 < \alpha < 1, 0 < \varphi < 1, 0 \leq \beta \leq 1$; $D_{0x}^{(\alpha,\varphi),\beta} y(x)$ -Hilfer ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli hosilasi [4].

$$D_{0x}^{(\alpha,\varphi),\beta} y(x) = I_{0x}^{\beta(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} I_{0x}^{(1-\beta)(1-\varphi)} y(x) , \tag{2}$$

$I_{0x}^\gamma y(x)$ – Riman-Liuvill ma'nosida γ (kasr) tartibli integral [5].

$$I_{0x}^\gamma y(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{\gamma-1} y(t) dt, \gamma > 0.$$

Koshi masalasi. Shunday $y(x)$ funksiya topilsinki, u quyidagi xossalarga ega bo'lsin:

- 1) $x^{(1-\beta)(1-\varphi)} y(x) \in C[0,1]$, $D_{0x}^{(\alpha,\varphi),\beta} y(x) \in C(0,1)$ sinfga tegishli
- 2) (1) tenlamani qanoatlantirsin;
- 3) $x = 0$ nuqtada esa

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} I_{0x}^{(1-\beta)(1-\varphi)} y(x) = A \tag{3}$$

shartni qanoatlantirsin, bu yerda, A - berilgan o'zgarmas haqiqiy son.

(1) tenglamani

$$I_{0x}^{\beta(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} I_{0x}^{(1-\beta)(1-\varphi)} y(x) - \lambda I_{0x}^\gamma y(x) = f(x) \tag{4}$$

ko'rinishda yozib olamiz.

(4) tenglamaga $D_{0x}^{\beta(1-\alpha)}$ ni ta'sir ettirib,

$$D_{0x}^{\beta(1-\alpha)} I_{0x}^\gamma y(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\beta(1-\alpha)+\gamma)} \frac{d}{dx} \int_0^x (x-z)^{\gamma-\beta(1-\alpha)} y(z) dz ,$$

$$D_{0x}^{\beta(1-\alpha)} y(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\beta(1-\alpha))} \frac{d}{dx} \int_0^x (x-z)^{-\beta(1-\alpha)} y(z) dz ,$$

formulalardan foydalanib, uni quyidagicha yozib olamiz;

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dx} I_{0x}^{(1-\beta)(1-\alpha)} y(x) - \frac{\lambda}{\Gamma(1-\beta(1-\alpha)+\gamma)} \frac{d}{dx} \int_0^x (x-z)^{\gamma-\beta(1-\alpha)} y(z) dz = \\ = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\beta(1-\alpha))} \frac{d}{dx} \int_0^x (x-z)^{-\beta(1-\alpha)} f(z) dz . \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

(6) ni 0 dan x gacha integrallab, uni quyidagicha yozib olamiz;

$$I_{0x}^{(1-\beta)(1-\alpha)} y(x) - \frac{\lambda}{\Gamma(1-\beta(1-\alpha)+\gamma)} \int_0^x (x-z)^{\gamma-\beta(1-\alpha)} y(z) dz =$$

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\beta(1-\alpha))} \int_0^x (x-z)^{-\beta(1-\alpha)} f(z) dz + A \tag{7}$$

ga $D_{0x}^{(1-\beta)(1-\varphi)}$ ni ta'sir ettirib,ba'zi

hisoblashlarni amalga oshirib, quyidagi

$$y(x) - \frac{\lambda}{\Gamma(\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi))} \int_0^x (x-z)^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)-1} y(z) dz =$$

$$= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\varphi+\beta(\alpha-\varphi))} \int_0^x (x-z)^{\varphi+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)-1} f(z) dz + \frac{Ax^{-(1-\beta)(1-\varphi)}}{\Gamma(1-(1-\beta)(1-\varphi))} \tag{8}$$

ko'rinishdagi ikkinchi tur Volterra integral tenglamasini hosil qilamiz.

(8) integral tenglamani yechish uchun ba'zi belgilashlarni kiritamiz:

$$g(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\varphi+\beta(\alpha-\varphi))} \int_0^x (x-z)^{\varphi+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)-1} f(z) dz + \frac{Ax^{-(1-\beta)(1-\varphi)}}{\Gamma(1-(1-\beta)(1-\varphi))} \tag{9}$$

$$K(x, z) = \frac{(x-z)^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)-1}}{\Gamma(\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi))} \tag{10}$$

(9) va (10) tenglamani ketma-ket yaqinlashish usuli orqali yechamiz.

$$K_1(x, z) = \frac{(x-z)^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)-1}}{\Gamma(\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi))} \text{ va } K_i(x, y) = \int_y^x K_1(x, t) K_{i-1}(t, y) dt$$

formulalardan foydalanib, ba'zi hisoblashlarni amalga oshirib, n – iteratsialangan yadroni

$$K_n(x, z) = \frac{(x-z)^{n(\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi))-1}}{\Gamma(n(\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)))}$$

ko'rinishda topamiz. $K_n(x, z)$ orqali $R(x, z, \lambda)$ rezolventani

$$R(x, z, \lambda) = \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\lambda^{n-1} (x-z)^{n(\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi))-1}}{\Gamma(n(\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)))}$$

ko'rinishda topamiz.

Integral tenglamalar nazariyasiga ko'ra tenglama yechimini,

$$y(x) = g(x) - \lambda \int_0^x R(x, z, \lambda) g(z) dz$$

ko'rinishda yozib olamiz, bu yerda

$$R(x, z, \lambda) = \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\lambda^{n-1} (x-z)^{n(\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi))-1}}{\Gamma(n(\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)))}$$

(9) va (10) belgilashlarni e'tiborga olib, ba'zi hisoblashlarni amalga oshirib, A masalaning formal yechimini

$$y(x) = Ax^{-(1-\varphi)(1-\beta)} E_{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi), 1-(1-\beta)(1-\varphi)} [\lambda x^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)}] +$$

$$+\int_0^x (x-z)^{\varphi+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)-1} E_{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi),\varphi+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)} [\lambda x^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)}] f(z) dz \quad (11)$$

ko'rinishda topamiz, bu yerda

$$E_{p,q}(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{z^n}{\Gamma(pn+q)} \quad (12)$$

- Mittag-Leffer funksiyasi [6].

Teorema. Agar $f(x) = x^{-P} f_1(x)$ bunda $p < 1 - \mu(1 - \alpha)$, $f_1(x) \in C[0,1]$ bo'lsa, u holda Koshi masalasining yechimi mavjud va u (11) formula bilan aniqlanadi.

Isbot. Dastlab (11) formulani (1) tenglamani qanoatlantirishini ko'rsatamiz. masala yechimni

$$y(x) = y_1(x) + y_2(x) \quad (13)$$

ko'rinishda yozib olamiz, bu yerda

$$y_1(x) = Ax^{-(1-\varphi)(1-\beta)} E_{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi),1-(1-\beta)(1-\varphi)} [\lambda x^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)}],$$

$$y_2(x) = \int_0^x (x-z)^{\varphi+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)-1} E_{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi),\varphi+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)} [\lambda x^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)}] f(z) dz.$$

Avval $y_1(x)$ ni (1) tenglamani qanoatlantirishini ko'rsatamiz. Buning uchun $I_{0x}^{(1-\alpha)(1-\beta)} y_1(x)$ ni hisoblaymiz:

$$I_{0x}^{(1-\alpha)(1-\beta)} y_1(x) = I_{0x}^{(1-\alpha)(1-\beta)} [Ax^{-(1-\varphi)(1-\beta)} E_{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi),1-(1-\beta)(1-\varphi)} [\lambda x^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)}]] \quad (14)$$

da ba'zi

hisoblashlarni amalga oshirib,

$$I_{0x}^{(1-\alpha)(1-\beta)} y_1(x) = AE_{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi),1} [\lambda x^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)}] \quad (15)$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz. (15) ni differensiallaymiz:

$$\frac{d}{dx} I_{0x}^{(1-\alpha)(1-\beta)} y_1(x) = A\lambda x^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)-1} E_{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi),\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)} [\lambda x^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)}] \quad (16)$$

(16) ni har ikki tarafini $I_{0x}^{\beta(1-\alpha)}$ ni ta'sir ettiramiz:

$$I_{0x}^{\beta(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} I_{0x}^{(1-\alpha)(1-\beta)} y_1(x) = I_{0x}^{\beta(1-\alpha)} [A\lambda x^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)-1} E_{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi),\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)} [\lambda x^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)}]] \quad (17)$$

(17) da ba'zi hisoblashlarni amalga oshirib,

$$I_{0x}^{\beta(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} I_{0x}^{(1-\alpha)(1-\beta)} y_1(x) = \lambda Ax^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta-\beta\varphi-1} E_{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi),\varphi+\gamma+\beta-\beta\varphi} [\lambda x^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)}] \quad (18)$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz.

Yuqoridagi kabi $I_{0x}^{\gamma} y_1(x)$ ni

$$I_{0x}^{\gamma} y_1(x) = Ax^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta-\beta\varphi-1} E_{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi),\varphi+\gamma+\beta-\beta\varphi} [\lambda x^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)}] \quad (19)$$

ko'rinishda topamiz.

(18) va (19) dan

$$I_{0x}^{\beta(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} I_{0x}^{(1-\beta)(1-\varphi)} y_1(x) - \lambda I_{0x}^{\gamma} y_1(x) = 0 \quad (20)$$

ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

Endi $y_2(x)$ ni (1) tenglamani qanoatlantirishini ko'rsatamiz.

Ko'rsatish qiyin emaski, quyidagi tenglik o'rinli bo'ladi:

$$I_{0x}^{(1-\beta)(1-\varphi)} y_2(x) = \int_0^x (x-z)^{-\beta(1-\alpha)} E_{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi), 1-(1-\alpha)\beta} [\lambda(x-z)^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)} f(z)] dz \quad (21) \quad (21)$$

da quyidagicha belgilash kiritamiz:

$$I_{0x}^{(1-\beta)(1-\varphi)} y_2(x) = g(x) \quad (22)$$

Ko'rish

qiyin

emaski

$$I_{0x}^{\beta(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} g(x) = \frac{d}{dx} I_{0x}^{\beta(1-\alpha)+1} g'(x) \quad (23)$$

tenglik o'rinli bo'ladi.

(22) va (23) dan foydalanib,

$$\frac{d}{dx} I_{0x}^{\beta(1-\alpha)+1} g'(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \frac{1}{\Gamma(1+\beta(1-\alpha))} \int_0^x (x-t)^{\beta(1-\alpha)} g'(t) dt \quad (24)$$

tenglikni yozib olamiz.

(24) da bir marta bo'laklab integrallash qoidasini qo'llab, $g(0) = 0$ va $\beta(1-\alpha) > 0$ ekanligidan

$$\frac{d}{dx} I_{0x}^{\beta(1-\alpha)+1} g'(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta(1-\alpha))} \int_0^x (x-t)^{\beta(1-\alpha)-1} g(t) dt$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz. (22) va (21) tengliklardan foydalanib, ba'zi soddalashtirishlarni amalga oshirib,

$$I_{0x}^{\beta(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} I_{0x}^{(1-\alpha)(1-\beta)} y_2(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \int_0^x f(z) E_{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi), 1} [\lambda x^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)}] dz \quad (25)$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz.

Bu yerda $E_{\delta, 1}(0) = 1$ ekanligini e'tiborga olib, parametr bo'yicha hosila olib,

$$I_{0x}^{\beta(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} I_{0x}^{(1-\alpha)(1-\beta)} y_2(x) = f(x) + \lambda \int_0^x (x-t)^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)-1} E_{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi), \varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)} [\lambda x^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)}] f(z) dz \quad (26)$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz.

Yuqoridagi kabi $I_{0x}^{\gamma} y_2(x)$ ni

$$I_{0x}^{\gamma} y_2(x) = \int_0^x (x-t)^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)-1} E_{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi), \varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)} [\lambda x^{\varphi+\gamma+\beta(\alpha-\varphi)}] f(z) dz \quad (27)$$

ko'rinishda topamiz.

(26) va (27) dan $y_2(x)$ ni (1) tenglamani qanoatlantirishi kelib chiqadi.

(15), (21) va $E_{\delta, 1}(0) = 1$ dan foydalansak, $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} I_{0x}^{(1-\varphi)(1-\beta)} y(x) = A$ kelib chiqadi.

Teorema isbotlandi.

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